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Availability Of Entrepreneurship Resources For Curriculum Implementation In Post-Basic Schools In Makurdi And Gwer-East, Benue State, Nigeria

***Kpadoo Vernimbe & Prof. Virginia Omada Alachi**

**Department of Arts and Social Sciences Education,
Faculty of Education,
Rev, Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University Makurdi, Nigeria
*Email: constancekpadooo@gmail.com**

ABSTRACT

The study investigated availability of entrepreneurship resources for curriculum implementation in post basic schools in Makurdi and Gwer-East Local Government Areas of Benue State, Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to determine the extent of the availability of entrepreneurship resources for curriculum implementation between urban and rural post basic schools. Five research questions guided the study while five null hypotheses were tested. Comparative descriptive research design was adopted. The population consisted of 410 entrepreneurial teachers from 32 schools. Proportionate stratified random sampling technique was used to select a sample of 230 entrepreneurship teachers. The instrument for data collection was a checklist with five-point rating scale titled “Entrepreneurship Resources for Curriculum Implementation Checklist” (ERCIC) which contained 50 items. The instrument was validated by four experts. A trial test was used to establish the reliability of the instrument. Data collected were analysed using Cronbach Alpha which yielded reliability coefficient value of 0.73. Mean and Standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that financial resources for curriculum implementation were available to a low extent (LE) in both urban and rural post basic schools (t-value = 2.392, 228; $p = 0.02 < 0.05$), instructional resources for curriculum implementation were available to a moderate extent (ME) in both urban and rural post-basic schools (t - value = 0.86, 228; $p = 0.39 > 0.05$). Based on these findings, it was concluded that the level of availability of entrepreneurship resources were inadequate for curriculum implementation in urban and rural post basic schools. It was therefore recommended that the State government should focus more on providing adequate funds for the purchase of entrepreneurship resources to enhance curriculum implementation in urban and rural post basic schools. The State Ministry of Education and other educational agencies should create educational resources centers that will serve as advisory resources to bridge the gap created by inadequate funding by the state government for implementation of entrepreneurship curriculum.

Keywords: Availability, Entrepreneurship, Resources, Curriculum, Implementation, Post basic schools.

INTRODUCTION

Curriculum is a vehicle through which knowledge and other learning activities are achieved. Curriculum plays an essential role in enabling quality learning in schools and in articulating and supporting education that is relevant to the holistic development of citizens in the 21st century (Ibeh, 2022). The intention behind the curriculum is to create a functional educational system in the country. Alachi and Agbum (2023) define curriculum as the means and materials with which students interact for the purpose of achieving identified educational outcomes. However, curriculum is defined, it has three important

components namely; the intended outcomes, what is taught and the manner of implementation Utulu (2021). Beyond a mere collection of subjects, the curriculum embodies a dynamic process evolving to meet the needs of diverse learners' societal changes and advancement in knowledge.

The objective of any level of education cannot be achieved if the planned programme for such a level of education is not well implemented. The problem of most curriculum design arises at the implementation stage. Implementation refers to the process of putting a plan, idea, design or system into action or practice (Ojengwa et al. 2024). It is the stage where concepts are translated into real world results by executing the necessary steps outlined in a blueprint. Implementation often involves deploying resources, managing tasks, and executing plans to achieve specific goals or objectives.

Curriculum implementation is one of the most critical elements of the curriculum process, yet it is the most neglected (Yang et al. 2013). It is one thing to develop or design a curriculum and it is another thing to implement it effectively. Curriculum implementation refers to how the planned curriculum is delivered in school. Odoh et al. (2018) assert that curriculum implementation is said to have taken place when the teacher-constructed syllabus, teacher personality, teaching materials and the teaching environment interact with the learner.

The educational sector is faced with the challenge of implementing the curriculum in the manner in which it is intended to be implemented. This is as a result of inadequate resources. The major problem affecting the implementation of curriculum in Nigeria today is the unavailability of teaching resources in most schools. The availability and quality of resource materials have a great influence on curriculum implementation.

The major element of curriculum is the teacher. It is the teacher that brings the curriculum document to limelight and to reality. The importance of teachers in curriculum planning, development and most importantly implementation cannot be overemphasized. This implies that the tasks of implementing the curriculum lies on the teacher. The teachers' role in curriculum development is an important one because the teacher is task with executing and implementing the curriculum document through effective transfer of knowledge and breaking down the contents into teaching units (Fasinro et al. 2024). Another element of curriculum is the student. The learner influences teachers in their selection of learning experiences. The content of the curriculum must be within their level for easy comprehension and understanding. The teachers must also take into consideration the individual differences of the students.

The third element concerned with curriculum is the availability and distribution of resources that will enhance the achievement of the teaching and learning objectives. Such materials include textbooks, instructional materials, desks and computer accessories. This is because for the curriculum content to be effectively implemented at any stage of the educational system, some materials which are expected to compliment the classroom activities of the teacher should be provided for effective implementation at the classroom levels of any of the educational programmes. Sometimes, when the curriculum is implemented without these resources, it becomes difficult for learners to assimilate lessons. Wotring et al. (2021) were of the view that comprehensive syllabus coverage enhances the likelihood of students achieving the intended learning outcomes specified in the curriculum and ensures that students are exposed to essential knowledge and skills. A well-covered syllabus prepares students for further education, ensuring they have a solid foundation in the subject.

However, it has been observed that the type of education obtained at all levels of education does not adequately equip the students with adequate skills to be self-sufficient. Omotayo et al. (2020) aptly observe that education has been reduced to a pattern of repeated practice when children go to primary, secondary and tertiary education to acquire certificates and start looking for non-existing jobs and in so doing they are trained to be job seekers and not employers of labour.

The government in an attempt to cure the challenges of unemployment and poverty in the country, government has introduced in the curriculum of post basic education trade/entrepreneurial subjects. As stated in the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014), about 34 entrepreneurship or trade subjects are taught in post basic schools across Nigeria. This was meant to provide students with diverse basic

knowledge on entrepreneurship, wealth creation, educational advancement and social development. It has become increasingly important to revert back more on educating students right from the beginning of their academic journey on entrepreneurship. Thus, certain skills become increasingly prominent to cope with the challenges of the age (Gurbuz & Aydin, 2022).

Entrepreneurship as a subject is very important for school leavers of post basic schools so much that it will help them develop into successful entrepreneurs after graduating from school. Entrepreneurship is a catalyst for economic development and job creation in any society and it involves rebranding the educational culture to the end of guaranteeing a comprehensive educational system. Dike and Effanga (2020) assert that educational main focus is to provide the students with requisite skills and capabilities needed in the world of work. Entrepreneurship requires to be taught for the transfer of all skills and knowledge from an expert to someone else. It involves an application of energy and passion towards the creation of an enterprise and these include willingness to take calculated risks; team work; having creative skills to marshal needed resources; fundamental skill of building solid business plan; and finally, having the vision to recognize opportunity where others see chaos, contradiction and confusion (Watkins-Marthys, 2009).

Entrepreneurship provides students with technical, economic and relevant business skills needed to be self-employed or start their own business in future. Ikeme (2012) as cited in Ugwude (2022) states that the benefits of entrepreneurship are to help students understand essential steps in starting a business, increase awareness of career and entrepreneurial options, understand basic financial concepts, management and social responsibility in the society. It develops students' creativity and improve their performance in schools, it makes students develop interest in school subjects and aid the realization of general goal of education. It creates employment opportunities for people and improves business start-up plan and management, it increases the level of economic competition among people.

The goals of entrepreneurship instituted in post basic school curriculum can only be achievable by ensuring that adequate resources are provided for effective implementation. Nations can compete based on a variety of factors such as abundant natural resources and by their skilled and educated work force. The achievement of the objectives of entrepreneurship curriculum in post basic school depends largely on the availability and the adequacy of resources for its effective implementation. To make entrepreneurship a success in post basic school curriculum, resources are crucial. Resource refers to any materials, substances and services that are used to produce products. A resource can be defined as a useful or valuable possession or means for support of man to make a living (Ugwude, 2022). Koehler (2019) defines resource as any factor that is necessary to accomplish a goal or carry out an activity.

Entrepreneurial resources are the tangible and intangible assets which firms use to exploit competitive imperfections in markets (Alvarez & Barney, 2014). They include assets, capabilities and networks that entrepreneurs need to start, grow and sustain their ventures. They can be tangible, such as money, equipment, or space or intangible such as skills, knowledge or connections. Entrepreneur students need access to resources as they learn how to start and run business so that they can benefit from the knowledge and experiences of their skill acquisition. In order for an entrepreneur to have expertise in a trade they need resources in order to access and analyze data so that they can make decisions about product design, marketing, pricing and other critical elements of their business. In essence, entrepreneurship curriculum is not only teaching someone to learn business. It also involves encouraging creative thinking and promoting a strong sense of self-worth and accountability (Nwosu, 2015).

There is the need for adequate provision of resources for effective entrepreneurship curriculum implementation in post basic schools. The only way by which post basic students can make informed decisions about their entrepreneurship is to use variety of resources to learn new skills and educate themselves on relevant issues. Abdulhameed (2014) state that entrepreneurship education has the mandate to equip the youth with the functional knowledge and skills to build up their skills, character, attitude, and vision.

Osuala and Oviawe (2010) states that the challenges of entrepreneurship education as follows: poor funding by government and non-governmental organization, inadequate employment of qualified teachers and instructors. Others are inadequate facilities and equipment for teaching and learning, poor planning, supervision and evaluation of the programme, as well as emphasis on theoretical knowledge rather than practical knowledge due to lack of entrepreneurship educational centers.

Adeyemi (2014) corroborated this view by maintaining that administrators of institutions of learning should be aware of existing regulation on the availability of entrepreneurship resources. Otamiri and Diseph (2022) state that in most schools, especially in south-south, Nigeria where these resources are likely to be available, there is also the question of their adequacy for effective instructional delivery especially in teaching entrepreneurship in business education.

Azih and Ani (2020) assert that high rate of unemployment among Nigerian school leavers demands that entrepreneurship education should be properly taught to students to enable them be self-employed. Entrepreneurship can bring about the desired remedy to this unacceptable situation of unemployment. It can be a tool for securing employment and emancipation of people through the provision and acquisition of necessary knowledge and skills to make life more meaningful for the citizens. Offem (2021) states that the quality and quantity of resources available and utilised in the school influence the level of interaction that exists between teachers and students. These entrepreneurship resources are as follows:

Financial Resources: Financial resources are crucial as they provide the necessary funding for entrepreneurship programme. Financial resources refer to money which every project requires for its effective implementation (Dike & Effanga, 2020). Funding such as cash, investment and loan is the most obvious form of financial resources. The post basic schools cannot perform optimally without funding. Chukwuma and Nwaham (2007), states that money provides the essential purchasing power with which education acquires its human and material input. In the absence of fund in an educational establishment, the educational objective will be a mirage.

Financial resources are necessary in implementing entrepreneurship scheme in post basic schools; it aids in providing all the necessary materials needed in a system. Ajibola (2008) notes that, no organization functions effectively without funds: the issue of poor financial resources has its manifestations in problems such as shortage of academic staff, dilapidated buildings and obsolete equipment. Izuagba (2010) observed that “the education industry is usually the first and the easiest victim of budget cut during reforms”. Also, Ayodele (2006) identified inadequate capital to be one of the principal factors hindering entrepreneurship education in public post basic schools.

Instructional Resources: It is significant to state that necessary instructional resources are very crucial in the teaching and learning of entrepreneurship curriculum. Eya and Ureme (2011) define instructional resources as materials which a teacher utilises in the course of presenting a lesson to make its content understandable to learners. The implication is that the use of instructional resources is inevitable if effective curriculum implementation is to be achieved. Dike (1987) as cited in Dike and Effanga (2020) described instructional materials as alternative channels of communication which a teacher can use to compress information and make them more vivid to his learners. Instructional resources are educational inputs that are of vital importance to the teaching of entrepreneurship subjects in the school curriculum. Acquisition of skills is enhanced by the provision of adequate instructional aids (Joseph & Iweyah, 2024). Instructional materials are ways and means of making the teaching and learning process easy, more meaningful and understanding. Babalola (2004) noted that instructional materials are designed to promote and encourage effective teaching/learning experiences. Ajayi (2009) in a study on relationship between availability of instructional materials and curriculum implementation in Nigeria secondary schools, discovered a significant level of relationship between these two. The provision of teaching aids and equipment such as interactive whiteboards and projectors, transforms traditional classrooms into hubs of interactive learning. This not only enhances the learning experiences but aligns with contemporary pedagogical approaches.

The integration of these tools into curriculum implementation process promotes active participation, knowledge retention and the achievement of curriculum implementation. These tools are essential parts of educational systems because they help teachers and students at all levels achieved their intended objectives. (Smith et al. 2023) Ogundele (2011) outlines examples of instructional resources in entrepreneurship education to include equipment, computer facilities, entrepreneurship textbooks, tools, farm lands and learning materials. These include textbooks, teaching aids, laptops, online courses and tutorials, multimedia resources, attending of workshop and conferences. These resources are vital for fostering entrepreneurial thinking.

Lack of instructional resources is a significant factor affecting effective curriculum implementation on entrepreneurship. Schools with limited access to instructional resources face challenges in keeping the curriculum relevant to current business environments (Fayolle & Gailly, 2018). Schools embedded in a robust instructional resource can provide students with mentorship opportunities and exposure to real world entrepreneurial challenge. In order to enhance effective curriculum implementation of entrepreneurship in post basic schools, there is need for provision of adequate instructional resources.

From the foregoing, it could be inferred that no meaningful teaching and learning takes place without adequate resource materials. Unavailability of these resources to teach students would likely lead to poor learning outcomes and also affects the teachers output. When post basic students are taught with adequate resources they could learn better. This may help improve the unemployment situation in the country. It is thus, imperative to find out the availability of entrepreneurship resources for curriculum implementation in post basic schools.

Statement of the Problem

The objective of introducing entrepreneurship curriculum by curriculum planners at post basic school level was to provide a functional education to graduating students in public schools as well as providing opportunity for the youth to become self-employed at the end of their education. Despite the introduction of entrepreneurship curriculum in post basic schools, students still graduate with little or no skill at all. There is a problem affecting implementation of entrepreneurship curriculum by the teachers. This could be as a result of unavailability of entrepreneurship resources which tends to affect students' ability to become self-reliant after graduation.

The unavailability of these resources affects curriculum implementation and leads to poor learning outcomes. This also affects the teachers' output thereby frustrating the objectives of the curriculum. The government, made frantic efforts to empower individuals with skill acquisition and knowledge of trade by introducing entrepreneurship curriculum in schools, which post basic school is one. The puzzle here is: How effective is entrepreneurship curriculum implemented in public post basic schools?

It is worthy to note that when adequate resources are provided in the required quality and quantity, the goal and objective of the government and curriculum planners will be achieved. This can reduce the level of unemployment in the society and also create self-reliance of fresh graduates thereby shifting attention from dependence on the government for white collar jobs. Successful implementation can also create wealth and boost the economic and social development of a nation. It is against this backdrop, that this study investigated availability of entrepreneurship resources for curriculum implementation between urban and rural post basic schools in Makurdi and Gwer-East Local Government Areas of Benue State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent are financial resources available for curriculum implementation between urban and rural post-basic schools?
2. To what extent are instructional resources available for curriculum implementation between urban and rural post-basic schools?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level:

1. There is no significant difference in the extent of financial resources available for curriculum implementation between urban and rural post-basic schools.
2. There is no significant difference in the extent of instructional resources available for curriculum implementation between urban and rural post-basic schools.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Design

Comparative descriptive design was adopted for this study. This type of research design is primarily used to describe and compare different variables or groups. This research design was concerned with providing a detailed and accurate snapshot of what was occurring or exists within the sample groups (Leedy & Ormrod, 2018).

The population of the study consisted of 410 entrepreneurship teachers from 32 post-basic government schools. The sample for this study comprised 230 teachers representing 57% of the population. All the schools in the population were used as sample for this study. The reason was because the number of the population was not large. Proportionate stratified random sampling technique was used in selecting post basic teachers in each school. Every school was represented based on the number of entrepreneurship teachers such schools possess.

The instrument used to elicit data for this study was Entrepreneurship Resources for Curriculum Implementation Checklist (ERCIC). It was divided into five clusters with 10 items each. ERCIC has five scales: Very Highly Extent (VHE) = 5, Highly Extent (HE) = 4, Moderate Extent (ME) = 3, Lowly Extent (LE) = 2 and Very Lowly Extent (VLE) = 1. The decision rule was based on the sum of the five-point scale divided by 5. Thus, $5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 = 15/5 = 3$. This implies that any option with 4.50 – 5.00 points is Very High Extent (VHE), 3.50 – 4.40 points is High Extent (HE), 2.50 – 3.49 points is Moderate Extent (ME), 1.50 - 2.49 points is Low Extent (LE) and 0.01 - 1.49 point is Very Low Extent (VLE).

The instrument was validated by four experts: One expert in Curriculum and Instruction, one expert in Social Studies Education, another expert in Entrepreneurship Studies and an expert in Test and Measurement, all from Rev Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. To ascertain the internal consistency of ERCIC, a trial test was carried out on 50 teachers who were part of the population, but not part of the main sample of the study. The data were computed using Cronbach Alpha. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, while t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent are financial resources available for curriculum implementation between urban and rural post-basic schools?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of the extent of financial resources available for curriculum implementation between urban and rural post-basic schools

S/N	Item	Urban			Rural		
		Mean	St. Dev.	Extent	Mean	St. Dev.	Extent
1	Government Funding	1.02	.530	VLE	1.08	.435	VLE
2	Funds from international organizations	2.65	.738	ME	2.97	.214	ME
3	School Budget Allocation	2.61	.745	ME	2.95	.252	ME
4	Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) Contributions	2.60	.746	ME	2.95	.211	ME
5	Corporate Sponsorships	1.97	.529	LE	2.05	.211	LE
6	Philanthropic Donations	2.13	.545	LE	2.04	.190	LE
7	Student Fees	2.14	.550	LE	2.06	.247	LE
8	Alumni Contributions	2.89	.606	ME	2.89	.370	ME
9	Loans	2.80	.588	ME	2.94	.230	ME
10	Partnership Funds	2.09	.514	LE	2.15	.357	LE
	Cluster	2.29	.609	LE	2.41	.272	LE

Key: VHE = Very High Extent, HE = High Extent, ME = Moderate Extent, LE = Low Extent, VLE = Very Low Extent

Table 1 reveals that financial resources for curriculum implementation were generally available to a low extent (LE) in both urban and rural post-basic schools, as indicated by the cluster mean scores of 2.29 (urban) and 2.41 (rural). Although rural schools have a slightly higher cluster mean, the difference was minimal, suggesting that both settings experience a comparable level of financial resource availability. This shows that government funding was insufficient and not available across both locations.

Research Question 2: *To what extent are instructional resources available for curriculum implementation between urban and rural post-basic schools?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of the extent of instructional resources available for curriculum implementation between urban and rural post-basic schools

S/N	Item	Urban			Rural		
		Mean	St. Dev.	Extent	Mean	St. Dev.	Extent
31	Classrooms	2.42	.880	LE	2.29	.494	LE
32	Entrepreneurial Labs	2.94	.550	ME	2.39	.490	LE
33	Furniture	2.38	.827	LE	2.41	.512	LE
34	Entrepreneurship Library	2.82	.481	ME	2.57	.515	ME
35	Transportation Vehicles	2.33	.552	LE	2.47	.502	LE
36	Storage Facilities	2.91	.407	ME	2.82	.383	ME
37	Workshops	2.76	.576	ME	2.78	.418	ME
38	Display Boards	2.67	.609	ME	2.67	.474	ME
39	Whiteboards and Markers	2.07	.467	LE	2.36	.483	LE
40	Projectors and Smartboards	2.07	.467	LE	2.23	.445	LE
	Cluster	2.54	.582	ME	2.50	.472	ME

Key: VHE = Very High Extent, HE = High Extent, ME = Moderate Extent, LE = Low Extent, VLE = Very Low Extent

Table 2 indicates that instructional resources for curriculum implementation were available to a moderate extent (ME) in both urban and rural post-basic schools. This was reflected in the cluster mean scores of 2.54 (urban) and 2.50 (rural). Although urban schools have a slightly higher cluster mean, the difference was minimal, showing that both setting experience nearly the same level of instructional resource availability.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the extent of financial resources available for curriculum implementation between urban and rural post-basic schools.

Table 3: Independent t-test of financial resources available for curriculum implementation between urban and rural post-basic schools

Variable Name	Location	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Diff.	Df	T	p	Remarks
Financial Resources	Rural	108	2.41	0.07	0.11	228	2.40	0.02	Significant
	Urban	122	2.29	0.48					

Table 3 shows that t-value = 2.392, with df = 228 and p = 0.018. Since p (0.02) < 0.05, the difference was statistically significant. The null hypothesis was rejected. This means there was a significant difference in financial resources available for curriculum implementation between rural and urban post-basic schools, with rural schools showing greater financial resource availability than urban schools.

Hypothesis 2:

There was no significant difference in the extent of instructional resources available for curriculum implementation between urban and rural post-basic schools.

Table 4: Independent t-test of instructional resources available for curriculum implementation between urban and rural post-basic schools.

Variable Name	Location	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Diff.	Df	T	p	Remarks
Instructional Resources	Rural	108	2.50	0.07	0.03	228	0.86	0.39	Not Significant
	Urban	122	2.54	0.46					

Table 4 shows that t-value = 0.859, with df = 228 and p = 0.392. Since p (0.39) > 0.05, the difference was not statistically significant. The null hypothesis was not rejected. This means there is no significant difference in the extent of instructional resources available for curriculum implementation between rural and urban post-basic schools. Although rural schools reported a marginally higher mean, the difference was not statistically meaningful.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding revealed that financial resources for curriculum implementation were generally available to a low extent both in urban and rural post basic schools. This suggest that availability of financial resources was poorly available for entrepreneurship curriculum implementation. This investigation is in line with Ayonmike (2014) which revealed that poor funding, obsolete facilities and inadequacy of instructional materials were affecting implementation of the Technical and Vocational Education and Training curriculum in Southern Nigeria technical colleges. This finding however, is in contrast with Gbemisola and Adeola (2015) which revealed 50% availability of funds for rural schools and 40% availability of funds for urban schools. This result indicate that funds were not made available for the implementation of entrepreneurship curriculum in post basic schools both in urban and rural post basic schools. From Table 1 above, it was observed that govt funding had a very low extent of availability of funds with the least mean of 1.02 in urban and 1.08 in rural post basic schools as compared to other sources of funding. Majority of the source of funds were realized from school fees, Alumni contributions and others. This shows that the State government has neglected to provide availability of funds for curriculum implementation of entrepreneurship curriculum in post basic schools.

The finding on Table 2 revealed that instructional resources for curriculum implementation were available to a moderate extent (ME) both in urban and rural post basic schools. This suggests the fact that instructional resources were not adequate enough though available to enhance effective curriculum implementation. This finding agrees with Alinno (2020) who assert that the current entrepreneurship curriculum in higher institutions was more theoretical and unsuitable for development of entrepreneurship practice and this was occasion as a result of shortage of instructional resources. The result of this study is also in line with Onyeachu (2008) who asserts that no matter how well designed, planned and documented the curriculum of any subject is planned; the core issue of outmost importance is the implementation modalities.

Curriculum Implications

Curriculum is the road map of learning. It plays an essential role in enabling quality education in post basic schools. The effectiveness of a curriculum has to do with its quality implementation in order to achieve desired goals. Availability of resources is one of the conditions that can determine effective entrepreneurship curriculum implementation. Based on the findings of this study, unavailability of resources was seen as a factor affecting entrepreneurship curriculum in post-basic schools in Gwer-East and Benue State Local Government Areas, of Benue State.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This present study established that entrepreneurship resources such as financial and instructional resources were not adequately available for implementation of entrepreneurship curriculum in urban and rural post basic schools in Makurdi and Gwer-East Local Government Areas, Benue State. The study also revealed that some of these resources were found to be available to a low extent (LE), while others were available to a moderate extent (ME). The State government should focus more on entrepreneurship education by providing funds adequately to ensure smooth curriculum implementation in post basic schools and instructional resources should be made available by school administrators in accordance with the proportion of the population of students in post basic schools. When this is done, it can prevent the situation where rural schools with less population of students have more resources as compared to urban schools with more population.

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